

Impacts of ENSO on the yield of paddy rice crops on a regional scale in Brazil, China, and Colombia

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Resumen— La Oscilación El Niño Sur (ENSO) es un fenómeno de variabilidad climática, cuyos efectos pueden inducir cambios en la temperatura y la precipitación en diferentes países del mundo. Estos eventos afectan a sectores de gran relevancia mundial, como la agricultura. Este estudio estimó el impacto de ENSO en los rendimientos de arroz en campos ubicados en Brasil, China y Colombia. Los impactos de la ENSO en la producción de arroz se midieron a través de las diferencias entre los rendimientos de las últimas dos décadas de cada cultivo en cada fase de la ENSO en comparación con las condiciones climáticas normales. La mayoría de los impactos estimados fueron ligeramente negativos, siendo los más significativos los reportados en la región de estudio en Brasil y Colombia durante la segunda temporada de cultivo, cuyo período de crecimiento coincide con el pico máximo de anomalías ENSO.

Palabras clave— ENSO, impactos, arroz

Abstract— The El Niño Southern Oscillation (ENSO) is a phenomenon of climatic variability, the effects of which can induce changes in temperature and rainfall in different countries of the world. These events impact sectors of great global relevance, such as agriculture. This research estimated the impacts of ENSO on paddy rice yields in fields located in Brazil, China, and Colombia. ENSO impacts on rice production were measured through the differences between the yields of the last two decades of each crop in each phase of ENSO compared to normal climatic conditions. Most of the estimated impacts were slightly negative, with the most significant impacts being those reported in the study region in Brazil and Colombia during the second growing season, whose growth period coincides with the maximum peak of ENSO anomalies.

Keywords— ENSO, impacts, Paddy rice

Introduction

Floods, droughts, and landslides, along with other extreme hydroclimatological events, have become more frequent and are bringing with them social, economic, and environmental costs. These phenomena are linked to climatic variability (CV) and climate change (CC) (**Venton2006**). El Niño-Southern Oscillation (ENSO) is the primary mode of tropical CV, with consequences on ecosystems, agriculture, freshwater supply and hydropower generation spanning most of the globe (**Dieppo2021**).

In Colombia, ENSO performs a significant influence in this country. For instance, in the warm phase, known as El Niño (EN), ENSO manifests with droughts and high temperature, unlike to its cold phase, known as La Niña (LN), which cause floods and decrease in temperature (**Poveda2011; Poveda2004**). For this country, the last extreme LN event in 2010-2011, the economy losses reached USD 4.87 billion (**Hoyos2013**). In the same way, the last extreme EN in 2015-2016, the Colombian economy was affected, causing a relative reduction to 5% of foods and inflation of 30.6% in its price (**Salcedo2016**).

On the other hand, in Brazil, ENSO manifests in different ways; in the subtropical strip (south), the warm phase of ENSO is manifested with an increase in rainfall and floods. On the contrary, LN is manifested with droughts and an increase in temperature (**Schossler2018**). While in the north (tropical strip) of this country, their effects are opposite, causing droughts during EN and an increase in rainfall during LN (**Oliveira1998; Melo1999**). This country's hydrology is regulated by climatic anomalies caused by the ENSO and the north atlantic oscillation (**Melo1999**). During EN in 2015–2016, Brazil suffered economic losses of around USD 300 million in the agricultural sector, causing a reduction of 1.6% in grain production (**martinez2017**). Meanwhile, during the LN of 2010–2011, this country invested close to USD 131 million to recover its agricultural sector and develop emergency works (**FAO2012**).

ENSO impacts not just rainfall in South American countries. In eastern China, EN is associated with a reduction in rainfall in the northern provinces and an increase in the southern provinces. During LN, the effects are opposite (**Gong1999; Fan2018; Zhou2007**). ENSO has impacts on grain production in China, affecting the stock market (**Anderson2018**).

According to the social, economic, and environmental importance that the ENSO phenomenon implies, it is necessary to develop and integrate strategies that allow adaptation to this type of natural event. For this reason, it is considered essential to strengthen scientific research to broaden knowledge of the dynamics and impacts of this type of phenomenon and favor the creation of response mechanisms and risk management in the national, regional, and local context.

Given the importance of agriculture in world food security and the economy, it is relevant to know ENSO events' impacts on crop yields. As mentioned above, ENSO causes anomalies in rainfall and temperature regimes, factors that can affect crop production anywhere in the world.

One of the major crops in the world is paddy rice. Rice feeds billions of people, and its cultivation is significant for food security (**Dong2016**). Paddy rice plants can grow in 120–140 days without a harvesting season, depending on the variety. The phenology of this plant develops in three stages: the vegetative stage, which includes the germination, seedling, tillering, and stem elongation; the reproductive stage, which includes the panicle initiation, heading, and flowering; and the maturation stage, which includes the milking, dough grain, and maturity grain (**Zheng2016**).

This research aims to estimate ENSO's impacts on paddy rice yields in three different parts of the world between 2000 and 2019. The selected regions were rice fields located in Brazil, China, and Colombia. The impacts were estimated, considering the yield and production data in each region of interest (ROI), and compared with the ONI index on the EN, LN, and neutral phases of this phenomenon. The crop's growth period was associated with the ENSO life cycle using the plant's mean phenology, which was estimated using MODIS images (MOD13Q1-006).

Methodology

Study area

In this study, three rice fields located in different regions of the world were selected (Fig. 1). The first ROI was located in Brazil ($57^{\circ}18'58''$ W, $30^{\circ}8'37''$ S) in the municipality of Barra do Quaraí and part of the municipality of Uruguaiana (State of Rio Grande do Sul), occupying an area of 1004km^2 (Fig. 1a). The second ROI was located in China ($112^{\circ}18'59''$ E, $29^{\circ}34'30''$ N), between the prefectures of Jingzhou, Yueyang, Yiyang, and Changde (between the provinces of Hunan and Hubei), occupying an area of 9632km^2 (Fig. 1b). Finally, the third ROI was located in Colombia ($75^{\circ}22'22''$ W, $2^{\circ}41'41''$ N) between the municipalities of Campoalegre and La Rivera (department of Huila), occupying an area of 197km^2 (Fig. 1c).

These countries represent tropical and subtropical regions with different climatic conditions. Each ROI was selected considering the descriptions made by other authors. In Brazil, the descriptions made by **Klering2008**, **Klering2013**, **Klering2016**, and **Mengue2019** were taken into account. Meanwhile, in China, descriptions made by **Peng2011**, **Zhao2016**, and **Liu2019**, were considered for this research. Finally, in Colombia the information provided by **Saavedra2018**, and **Gutierrez2018** were examined for this ROI.

Data acquisition

The rice fields were identified with MODIS images (MOD13Q1-006) acquired from 2000 to 2019. MOD13Q1-006 provides vegetation indices such as NDVI that are used to extract the mean phenology of each of the selected crop areas (Fig. 2). The collection of images was acquired through the

Figure 1: Regions of interest. (a) Brazil. (b) China. (c) Colombia

Google Earth Engine (GEE) platform. Each growing area was previously identified with Google Earth images.

Rice yield and production data were downloaded from the Brazilian Institute of Statistics and Geography (**IBGE2021**), the National Bureau of Statistics of China (**NBS2021**), the United Nations Organization for Agriculture and Food (**FAO2012**) and the National Administrative Department of Statistics of Colombia (**DANE2016**).

The Oceanic Niño Index (ONI) data were acquired from NOAA to identify the El Niño and La Niña events (<https://psl.noaa.gov/enso/dashboard.neut.html>). ONI is based on a 3-month running mean of SST anomalies in the Niño 3.4 region ($^{\circ}5\text{ N}$ - $^{\circ}5\text{ S}$, $^{\circ}170$ - $^{\circ}120\text{W}$) from ERSSTv5, relative to a 30-year climatology. El Niño and La Niña are defined when the ONI reaches the threshold of $+0.5^{\circ}\text{C}$ and -0.5°C for at least five consecutive overlapping 3-month averages. The period considered in this study was between 2000(DJF) to 2019(DFJ).

Phenology

A smoothing method was used to detect the mean phenology of paddy rice cultivation throughout the study period; a second-order local polynomial regression (LOESS) was applied (Eq. 1).

$$\hat{y} = \hat{\beta}_0^i + \hat{\beta}_1^i x_i + \hat{\beta}_2^i x_i^2 \quad (1)$$

Where the $\hat{\beta}^i$ is the estimate of the smoothing parameters for each point x_i , additionally, a span ($\Delta(x)$) of 0.5 was adopted, which indicates that 50% of its neighbors were selected to estimate the curve at each point closer to X_0 . For the assignment of the weights of the observations close to the x_0 estimation point, the tricube function was chosen (Eq. 2 and 3).

$$u = \frac{x_i - x_0}{\Delta(x)} \quad (2)$$

$$W(u) = \begin{cases} (1 - u^3)^3 & \text{when } 0 \leq u \leq 1 \\ 0 & \text{in other case} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

u consists of the set of neighbors closest to the focal point x_0 , and W are the weights assigned by the tricube function.

Anomalies

The standardized anomaly index (SAI) was used to estimate the anomalies in each set of crop yield data (Eq. 4).

Figure 2: Flowchart to define the mean growth period of crops. The methods comprise of GEE cloud platform and local processing

$$x = \frac{x_t - \bar{x}}{\sigma} \quad (4)$$

x_t represents the variable's annual value to be standardized, and \bar{x} and σ represent its mean and standard deviation. The trend and seasonality effects were removed using the "difference" method ($\nabla_{x_t}^d$) (Eq. 5).

$$\nabla_{x_t}^d = (1 - B)^d x_t \quad (5)$$

where B is the backshift operator ($B_{x_t}^k = x_{t-k}$ for $k \geq 1$).

Impacts of ENSO on crop yields

The negative and positive impacts of El Niño and La Niña on yield anomalies for each paddy rice crop field were applied, taking into account the considerations made by **Iizumi2014** and **Anderson2017** using the following equations:

$$Y_{ENSO\ phase} = \frac{1}{n_{ENSO\ phase}} \sum_{t=2000}^{2019} \%Y_{anomalies\ ENSO\ phase} \quad (6)$$

$$Y'_{ENSO\ phase} = \frac{\sum W_c \cdot Y_{ENSO\ phase}}{\sum W_c} \quad (7)$$

$$\Delta Y_{El\ Nino} = Y'_{ENSO\ El\ Nino} - Y'_{ENSO\ Neutral} \quad (8)$$

$$\Delta Y_{La\ Nina} = Y'_{ENSO\ La\ Nina} - Y'_{ENSO\ Neutral} \quad (9)$$

Where $\%Y_{anomalies\ ENSO\ phase}$, $Y_{ENSO\ phase}$, $Y'_{ENSO\ phase}$, W_c , $n_{ENSO\ phase}$, and $\Delta Y_{El\ Nino-a}$ are the standardized anomaly yields (%), percentage yield anomalies for each phase, percentage yield anomalies over the cropping systems for each phase, production of the crop, number of each ENSO phase, and the impacts of El Niño and La Niña on yield anomalies.

The significance of the difference between the average percentage yield anomaly in El Niño years and that in neutral years, that is, $\Delta Y_{El\ Nino-a}$, was tested at each paddy rice field using the bootstrap method with 1000 iterations (considering an interval confidence of 95% in the standard normal distribution).

Results and discussion

ENSO life cycles and crop phenology

Figure 3 shows the mean phenology (using NDVI) for each ROI throughout 2000-2019. In Brazil (Figure 3a), rice begins its mean growing cycle between the day of the year (doy) 321 (in Novem-

ber) and 97 (in April). Meanwhile, the heading phase is reached between doys 1 (in January) and doys 33 (in February). The results reported in Figure 3a follow the calendar phenology reported by MaClean2013, Cordeiro2017, and CONAB2019.

Figure 3b shows the mean rice phenology for a single rice crop system in China ROI selected. In doys 161 (in June) starts the cultivation until the doys 305 (in October), including the harvesting phase. In the doys 225 (in August), the crops reach their heading phase. Authors such as Wang2015 had reported similar results in Deqing county (North Zhejiang province -China), with a maximum of these indices during the heading stage of 0.5-0.7 between August and September and 0.3 and 0.2 beginning its decline in the maturity stage in October.

In Colombia (Fig. 3c), rice is cropped twice a year. The first crop starts in doys 65 (in March) and ends in doys 193 (in July); the heading phase is reached in doys 113 (in April). Meanwhile, the second crop starts in doys 257 (in September) and ends between the doys 1 and 17 (in January); in this season, the heading phase is reached in doys 321 (in November).

Figure 3: Paddy rice phenologies using the NDVI. (a), (b), and (c) correspond to the rice phenology in the areas selected in Brazil, China, and Colombia. The green and blue horizontal lines denote the day of the year (doy) at the start, heading, and end dates for the crops. In Colombia, paddy rice is cropped twice a year

According to the ENSO life cycles shown in figures 4 and 5, the maximum (for El Niño) and minimum (for La Niña) peaks are reached in October-November-December (OND) during the boreal winter and tend to decay (increase) to neutral conditions in April-May-June (AMJ) during the boreal spring (Figs. 4a and 5(a,c)).

The crop calendars shown in figures 4b and 5b were adapted according to the results obtained in this investigation (Fig. 3). For Brazil (Br), China (Cn), and Colombia (Co), the crop cycle was approximately centered with the heading phases, covering a threshold between -2 and +2 months

(including harvesting time). According to each phenology defined, ENSO events overlap the crops, with different intensities of this phenomenon being less (or more) sensitive to climate fluctuation (in lag = 0).

Figure 4: a). El Niño composite with ONI. The bold black line represents the mean. b). Paddy rice growing seasons in each country. The numbers in Colombia indicate the two growing seasons in the year

ENSO impacts over crop yields

Figures 6, 7, and 8 show the normalized yield and production values in each ROI that have been used to estimate the standardized yield ($\%Y_{anomaliesENSOphase}$) and production anomalies (W_c) of

a.

—■— 1998 —◆— 2005 —▼— 2007 * 2010 —*— 2016 —●— mean

b.

c.

—■— 1999 —◆— 2000 —▼— 2008 * 2017 —●— mean

Figure 5: a.) La Niña composite with ONI. c.) Composite of La Niña with ONI in prolonged La Niña events. b). Paddy rice growing seasons in each country. The numbers in Colombia indicate the two growing seasons in the year

the paddy rice areas associated with every ROI (Eq. 6 and 7). In Brazil and China, the means of Normalized values of municipalities and provinces that cover these ROI were selected (Fig. 6f, 6h, 7f, and 7g).

Figure 6: Rice yield and production in the municipalities corresponding to the selected ROI in Brazil. (a), (b), (c), and (d) correspond to the records of yields and production in the municipalities of Barra do Quaraí and Uruguaiana. (e), (f), (g), and (h) represent normalized and trendless data for yields and production. The red line indicates the applied linear regression models, and the dotted red line at (f) and (h) denotes the mean values of yield and normalized production

According to the results obtained, the ENSO phases' impacts on the average performance anomalies vary in each ROI. Figure 9 shows the impacts in terms of percentage, taking as reference the crop's yield during the neutral phase of the ENSO. Positive (negative) values denote positive (or negative) impacts regarding crop yield during the EN (LN) phase.

In Brazil's ROI, the EN showed a negative impact of -6.72 % (95 % confidence interval (CI): -14.134, 0.695), which means that the rice yield between 2000 and 2019 reached a reduction of

Figure 7: Rice yield and production in the prefectures corresponding to the selected ROI in China. (a), (b), (c), and (d) correspond to the records of yields and production in the prefectures of Hunan and Hubei. (e), (f), (g), and (h) represent normalized and trendless data for yields and production. The red line indicates the applied linear regression models, and the dotted red line at (f) and (h) denotes the mean values of yield and normalized production

Figure 8: Rice yield and production in the Department corresponding to the selected ROI in Colombia. (a), (b), (c), and (d) correspond to the records of yields and production in two crop seasons in the department of Huila. (e), (f), (g), and (h) represent normalized and trendless data for yields and production. The red line indicates the applied linear regression models, and the dotted red line at (f) and (h) denotes the mean values of yield and normalized production

Figure 9: Impacts. Red rectangle corresponds to El Niño. The blue rectangle corresponds to La Niña. Brazil (a, b), China (c,d), Colombia first season (d,e), and Colombia second season (f,g). t^* is the bootstrap estimate (mean of bootstrap realizations)

6.72 % compared to neutral conditions (Fig. 9a). The opposite case occurs during La Niña, whose performance is favored by an increase of 4.52 % (C.I. 95 %: 1.815, 7.234) in its performance (Fig. 9b). Authors such as **Cirino2015** and **Iizumi2014** reported similar impacts on rice yields in large extensions of land in which the study area defined in this research is contained.

On the other hand, EN and LN showed slight negative impacts on rice cultivation concerning neutral ENSO conditions in China. These percentages had an impact of -0.39 % (during LN; CI 95 %: -2.1650, 1.3753) and -0.23 % (during EN; CI 95 %: -1, 8596, 1.3514). The low impacts reported are linked with the decay phase of ENSO and the periods of paddy rice cultivation in this ROI **Gong1999**. Authors such as **deng2010** and **Iizumi2014** have reported impacts similar to those reported in this study.

In each of the growing seasons in Colombia, different degrees of impact occurred. During the first phase of rice cultivation, ENSO was in its decay phase, impacting -0.7% (during El Niño; 95% CI: -2.9078, 1.5002) and 0.55% (during LN; 95% CI: -6.0718, 7.1689). On the other hand, during the second growing season, when the ENSO reaches its maximum peaks, the impact on rice yield increases by -2.40% (during EN; 95% CI: -6.733, 1.436) and -3.10% (during LN; 95% CI: -6.674, 0.503).

Crop phenology is subject to changes in ENSO. These changes generate positive or negative impacts on the life cycle of each phase of ENSO. During the disintegration phase (JJA) the rice crops grown in these periods are slightly impacted, showing a slight contrast in terms of their difference with the neutral conditions of ENSO. In contrast, crops grown in corresponding periods at the ENSO peak (OND) show higher impacts on crop yield than crops cultivated in the decay phase of ENSO.

Positive impacts on crop yields with respect to ENSO were reported in Brazil and Colombia (first season) during LN. Concerning this, other factors apart from ENSO, such as agricultural technology and socioeconomic decisions, can influence crop yields. In the case of Brazil ROI, the positive impacts reported during drought conditions (in LN), can be mitigated by improvements in irrigation techniques **pinto2020**. Unlike Brazil, the positive impacts in Colombia's first season ROI were low with respect to normal weather conditions, and it has been benefited by the slight effects of LN (with a low increment in rainfall) during its decaying period.

Conclusion

ENSO events have significant effects on agriculture, influencing crop yields. The impacts of ENSO estimated on large-scale crops such as rice show that the influences of CV phenomena such as ENSO can be measured at local or regional levels, giving more details about the ENSO teleconnection in crops. In future studies, it will be of great importance to evaluate the vulnerability of crops and the socioeconomic consequences correlated with this event of climatic variability.

Regarding the impacts of ENSO events on rice yield in Brazil, China, and Colombia, these crops are primarily impacted when their growth phase occurs during the November-January period in which EN (LN) reaches its maximum peak of anomalies. Meanwhile, during the decaying phase of ENSO, crop yields are a little impacted with respect to neutral conditions; additionally, technological contributions in irrigation activities can mitigate the negative impacts of climate variability phenomena such as ENSO.